

ER4STEM REPOSITORY

[DELIVERABLE 5.4]

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ER4STEM - EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS FOR STEM

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2 DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

Version Number	Date	Description	Author
V1	09/05/2018		Annalise Duca
V2	29/06/2018	Partial Review	Julián M. Ángel-Fernandez
V3	03/08/2018	Additional texts	Angele Giuliano
V4	21/09/2018	Additional functions	Angele Giuliano

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5 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

5.1 ROLE/PURPOSE/OBJECTIVE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This document is a report which outlines and explains all the steps undertaken to identify, create and deploy the ER4STEM repository in relation to Work Package 5, titled “*Technology for Educational Robotics*”. The ER4STEM educational repository is aimed at teachers, robotics practitioners and researchers across Europe to help make resources for robotics in education easily available and helps educators make use of robotics during their lessons.

5.2 RELATIONSHIP TO OTHER ER4STEM DELIVERABLES AND TASKS

Deliverable 5.4 is directly linked to Deliverable 1.4 “ER4STEM Framework” and Deliverables D4.2 and D4.3 “ER4STEM Activity Plan”. In fact, the data from these has informed the creation of the database structures behind the repository. There are also links to WP2-D2.4 for curriculum, WP3-D3.4 for robotics competitions and also WP8-D8.2 for academic papers

5.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document takes on a narrative structure on the evolution of the repository from its inception, to its design and up to the final deployment. It is meant to show the technical development that was supported by the pedagogical experts to create a final solution that is useful to teachers all over Europe.

6 INTRODUCTION

The ER4STEM project has as one of its main objectives to create structures, content and awareness amongst the European teaching community for a better inclusion of robotics into mainstream education. Through this, the ultimate aim is to inspire students to start enjoying more the STE(A)M subjects. This report relates to deliverable 5.4 “ER4STEM Repository” and is a collection of activities performed during the project period, with regards to idea realisation, development and implementation of the repository.

6.1 AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The preliminary aims and objectives of the repository are to provide an easy-to-use portal that can be used by the identified target audience of the project. As per the description of work, the repository was developed based on the findings of T1.1 (Best Practises and Requirements) and the activity template created in WP4 and reported in D4.1.

The main objective of the repository is to facilitate and aims at making it easier for users to locate and use resources related to robotics during lessons, competitions or workshops. As per the findings of Deliverable 1.1, we found many different approaches in educational robotics, however most of these are outside of school, defragmented and unconnected. Citing one of the results from that deliverable: *"The many existing educational resources regarding robotics are based on the technology they use. There is a need for a user- and activity-centered repository. This can only be achieved by a better understanding of the stakeholders engaged in educational robotics."*

Further to this, technology is being implemented in the classroom, however it is not integrated correctly to improve the learning process (Schleicher, 2015).

Finally, this tool will be made available to SCIENTIX ambassadors and promoted through the SCIENTIX Portal.

6.2 IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

The stakeholders for the ER4STEM repository have been identified through brainstorming sessions held between partners during a face-to-face meeting in Malta. These include but are not limited to (D1.1 and D1.2):

- **Young Learners:** These include students who are studying or otherwise have an interest in robotics, and would like to learn more on robots and robotic kits available.
- **Universities**
 - Educational Researchers: are in the field of education, looking to find previous research that took place, with regards to educational robotics
 - Robotics Researchers: come from different fields to developed new technologies and algorithms to improve the field of robotics.
 - Teacher Educators: Teachers at University level
 - Outreach with Educational Robotics activities
- **Schools**
 - Teachers: Teachers at primary, secondary or tertiary level, who wish to start making use of robotics in their classroom, in different domains

- School's Board: School's board, which although might also be teachers, can make decisions with regards to the technology being used in their school and are involved in the decision-making processes related to implementing improvements within the regular school curricula in different subject areas, including those related to the STEAM domains
- Senior Management: This team normally has the final word with regards to school decisions
- **Organisations offering ER:** The below are 3 different types of organisations who offer out-of-school courses, activities in relation to educational robotics.
 - Non-profit
 - Profit
 - Science and technology institutes
- **Industry**
 - ER tools as a product: Companies who create, develop and sell robotic kits and technologies for educational or non-educational purposes
 - Human Resources
- **Parents:** Parents who would like to encourage their kids more in relation to using robotics to study
- **Policy-makers:** People who make decisions that affect the whole ecosystem
- **Ministries of Education:** Educational decision makers, who decide the way forward when it comes to education.

Hence from the above list, one identifies that the main impact of the project will be for: **Educators, Researchers and Organisations offering Educational Robotics.**

Educators:

These include teachers, head of schools and curricula creators, that work closely in education with students of different ages. Since our project is aimed at 3 different target groups (i.e. 7 to 10, 11 to 14 and 15 to 18), the repository also reaches and targets such educators across different levels of education.

Researchers:

Universities and researchers who are following research in various topics such as science, technology, engineering, mathematics, robotics and education, are also aimed.

Organisations offering Educational Robotics:

Finally the last group of stakeholders includes organisations (both non-profit organisations and profit organisations) who offer courses for kids, youth or adults about robotics. These courses can range from 1-day workshops to diplomas. Using the ER4STEM repository can help them get inspiration for lessons and also to use different robotic kits as well as find tools and materials for the adaptation and implementation of educational robotics activities

Secondary stakeholder impacted by the outcomes of ER4STEM: Industry. We believe that apart from reaching the above mentioned stakeholders, the project and the repository can have a direct impact on the robotics industry. I.e companies who are developing and producing education robotics kits. Such companies have the opportunity to share and disseminate specific lesson plans that they have using their educational robotics kit with educators.

Moreover there is also a wider industry perspective for example the ICT industries or else research based organisations where robotics is an interesting skill that they would want their employees to have.

6.3 STAKEHOLDERS NEEDS AND REQUIREMENTS

Different techniques have been used in order to identify and collect the stakeholders needs and requirements. Using different techniques allowed us to ensure that diverse opinions and requirements are collected across different stakeholders.

6.3.1 Brainstorming Workshops

Initial identification has been done by holding different brainstorming sessions. These sessions have been recorded using mind-mapping tools and have been done with different team players. These include, creative members, technical and non-technical experts. Further to this, during such brainstorming sessions, identification of different business scenarios will be an important aspect of the discussion to ensure that the repository is also sustainable after the end of the project.

6.3.2 Interviews/Questionnaires with Stakeholders

To get a broader perspective, one-to-one interviews (where possible) and an online questionnaire were created in order to collect information regarding first hand real needs when it comes to repositories and robotics. A number of questions were posed to different stakeholders to identify the perceived and expressed needs.

Following this, all needs identified have undergone a selection process to ensure that a feasible, but yet useful repository has been developed.

(i) INTERVIEWS - SCIENTIX 45 MIN WORKSHOP

On the 28th February 2016 during the second Scientix conference, a 45-minute workshop was done with STEM teachers to identify possible requirements in relation to educational robotics. Below is a detailed agenda of the workshop. The results are listed here as main points:

The availability of materials (robotic kits) is an issue in many schools. Suggestions:

Materials exchange between schools or a physical repository with materials and lesson plans offered by a third-party organization.

Teacher training: There are not robotics teachers yet. STEM teachers need help with lesson plans. They are not the experts in robotics as they are the experts in their subjects. Primary school teachers are generalists; they feel like they need the experts in the classroom.

Lesson plans are not linked to curricula. They should be modular, linked to topics in curricula and age group (or cognitive capabilities and prior knowledge requirements). Or there should be a new subject like coding that can be easily linked with robots. Lesson plans or activity descriptions are too long. There is a need for quick previews, better graphical interface to access the information needed. Video tutorials would be very helpful.

Teaching “anything” with robotics: Why use robotics to teach something else than robotics? There is a need for lesson plans or what-if concepts and guidance for teachers to understand how various topics can be taught through robotics.

Software: to control different robotic kits. Interactive materials like virtual robots that can be accessed via internet are needed.

Projects: More international projects for schools to participate in.

(ii) ECER TEACHER WORKSHOP (2 HOURS)

During ECER 2016 in Vienna a workshop for Scientix ambassadors and STEM teachers was held with the following main questions:

- What tools do you currently use and why?
- What is missing? What do you think is needed for you to consider the use of robots in the classroom or have a better teaching impact?

The ensuing discussion was very useful and allowed us to understand more the current scenario in the different schools, not only in Austria but also in other countries. The feedback obtained in this workshop has helped us to create part of the use cases related to educators. The general result was that yes, there is a clear need for robotics educational resources and for more support for teachers (see next chapter for more details of the results)

(iii) ANALYSIS QUESTIONNAIRE

An analysis questionnaire, that is similar to a needs analysis, was created. The aim behind this questionnaire was to get a first-hand response from educators, researchers and relevant stakeholders on what they feel is missing when it comes to Educational Robotics. All partners shared this questionnaire with the relevant stakeholders. AcrossLimits also used this questionnaire during an introductory meeting of the Malta workshops with the teachers that were invited from different schools across Malta that was held on 17th March 2016 at the Kulleġġ San Ġorġ Preca - Ħamrun ĠP Primary, Ġuże Paċe Street, Ħamrun ĦMR1032.

The questionnaire is found as Appendix 2 at the end of this document. It was converted to an interactive online questionnaire using JotForm to help collect easily the information from the stakeholders of the project.

The below is an analysis from the answered received in relation to the Needs Analysis. A total of 45 stakeholders shared their opinion.

ARE TEACHERS ALREADY MAKING USE OF ROBOTS IN THE SCHOOL?

The following figure illustrates that 60% of the respondents stated that they are already making use of robots in the school, with the rest claiming that they haven't use robotics in their school.

WHAT SUBJECTS DO YOU USE IT FOR AND WHICH ROBOT TECHNOLOGIES ARE YOU USING?

When asked what subjects, do these stakeholders use robotics for, and the technologies that they are using, the answers varied, however the majority are making use of Lego Mindstorms.

- Arduino, Lego Mindstorms
- Summer school only at this point, but hope to expand into science.
- programming with scratch
- making robots with LEGO
- we are using LEGO WeDo
- Robotics - Computer Studies / ICT... Lego MindStorms
- Programming, Environmental projects. LEGO EV3, Arduino, Raspberry
- I use Lego Mindstorms NXT and EV3 Education sets. Our students practice and improve their programming skills through robotics during a computer science course. Also, in our school students have the opportunity to join robotic clubs and participate in WRO contests.
- Lego WeDo, Probot, Beebot. During ICT lessons"
- Beebot for Maths
- Beebot / Constructa-Bot for English and maltese lessons
- Yes, in after school activities. EVS Lego Mindstorm
- No, but we are working on a Level 2 programme on Robotics. The college already invested in a couple of Lego Mindstorms
- ICT, science and maths. We have a beebot and a probot.
- Science, IT
- Lego mindstorms, just bought, we are on the learning curve
- Mainly for Mathematics; BeeBots and a ProBot.
- Computing
- Computer studies & digital literacy. Technology used is EV3 lego mindstorms
- Computing, NXT mindstorms
- Scratch Lego Mindstorms EV3 (whole range incl extension kits, pneumatics kits etc)

- Lego WeDo Beebots Probots Lego software
- Lego Mindstorms with form 3 (Grade 9) computing students

WHICH ONLINE RESOURCES/PORTALS DO YOU ALREADY MAKE USE IN YOUR TEACHING?

When asked about the resources/portals that the educators already make use of, 22 out of 45 participants said that they do not make use of portals and others mentioned portals like SCIENTIX, OpenEducationEuropa, European Schoolnet, Edmodo, and the robotic kit platform.

WHICH OF THESE FEATURES WOULD YOU MAKE USE OF IN AN PORTAL THAT WOULD BE DEDICATED TO ROBOTICS?

Features - Most Voted

The stakeholders were also asked which features they would make use of on the portal. The answers varied, with participants selecting more than one. The 2 most popular options were videos and tutorials, followed by a Web Application.

WHICH OF THE FOLLOWING RESOURCES WOULD YOU LIKE TO SEE?

Participants were also asked about which resources they would like to see on the portal. Both “Lesson plans/Activity Plans” and “Games using robotics” got 39 votes, followed by “Workshops” and “Educational Technologies”.

Which of the following resources would you like to see?

IF YOU HAD TO CHOOSE THE FILTERS BY WHICH YOU SEARCH RESOURCES. WHICH ONES WOULD YOU PREFER?

Participants were given the option to sort from 1-7 (1 being the most important) on the fields that they would prefer searching to be done. As the below matrix shows, Age and Language were the two most voted fields with 14 and 13 votes each. This is followed Curriculum, which got the highest preferences with 9 votes.

Points scored

The collected data from this questionnaire, can be found in Appendix 2 of this document.

DATA EXTRACTION, ANALYSIS AND OUTCOMES

Based on the results provided, the most requested features have been given priority. Further analysis have been done on open ended questions.

6.3.3 Robotics Portals Analysis

ROBOTIC PORTALS FEATURES MATRIX

The below matrix visualises the analysis being done on other online robotics portals with regards to 5 different indicators. Each platform is rated on a scale of 1 to 5, with 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest score.

	Target Audience	User-Friendliness	Searching Parameters	Content	Robotic Related Content
SCIENTIX	5	5	4	4	2
Open Education Europa	3	2	5	4	2
OER Commons	3	4	5	3	4
Consumer Classroom	3	5	3	3	1
Platform based Repositories	4	3	2	3	5

1. Scientix

In this portal (Scientix, 2015), users can find teaching materials, report libraries, training courses and LRE materials, although the focus is not only Science, most of the material is related to STEM education.

Target Audience: This community is focused on science related material and aimed to reach national teachers.

User-friendliness: As a portal, navigation is very easy, and it has a very clean layout to avoid any confusion. Further to this, users can request free translation of the learning resources.

Searching Parameters: Users can search by one or more of the following fields: subject, minimum and maximum age, type of resource and language.

Content: Currently, there could be found over 1.850 resources in different subjects and fields. Each resource contains tags, age range, resource type, author and a description.

Robotic related Content: Content related to robots is of approximately three resources.

2. OpenEducationEuropa

In this portal (Europa), users can find or share information with others. Users can find MOOC's, Courses, Resources and even institutions.

Target Audience: The portal is aimed at teachers, researchers and educators across different areas of knowledge.

User-friendliness: The search feature is very visible, with a slightly less visible "Advanced Search". Overall, the website main page is always updated with new information, and this might confuse where one should press to proceed.

Searching Parameters: After introducing a keyword, the user will be able to filter the content and obtain a more refined search. Content can be refined by type, institution, language, features, subject, licenses and education level.

Content: Over 66.000 results from different content types (although over 44.000 are user profiles) could be found. The content for each resource varies according to the type, however for learning resources this includes educational level, languages, licenses, tags and type. The portal also allows users to comment within the resources with an account. Further to this, sharing via email, twitter and Facebook is also available.

Robotic related Content: Content related to robots is of approximately over 200 resources.

3. OERCommons

The OER Commons portal (Commons, 2015) is very welcoming upon landing on the site. It is very well structured with an easy to use tool for users to search for materials. The portal can also be used to create and connect with others.

Target Audience: The portal is aimed at individuals or organizations that would like to share or else find resources to reuse with their colleagues or students. Most of these resources follow a Creative Commons or GNU License. This will allow the material to be used, reused, adapted and shared according to the author rights.

User-friendliness: As previously mentioned, it has a very clean and modern design. A very useful tool is the Learner Options. This feature allows the user browser to change the text size, the text style, line spacing and the colour and contrast.

Searching Parameters: Users can search by free text, subject, education level and standard. Upon searching one can refine the search by education standard, subject area, education level, material type, conditions of use, content source, primary user, media format and educational use.

Content: Over 64.000 resources can be found in this portal. For each resource, further information such as provider, level, grades and abstract can be found. Comments can also be left for each

resource without the need to log in. Any resources found can be saved by the user once an account is created.

Robotic related Content: Over 280 resources are available related to Robotics.

4. Consumer Classrooms

This portal (Classroom C.) is rather a tool that is to be used by the teachers, including also the searching of resources.

Target Audience: This tool is aimed at teachers to showcase an extensive library of consumer education resources from across the EU.

User-friendliness: The website is very user-friendly with specific banners for different tools and features available. An interesting feature is the Lesson Builder, where users can create their own lessons for the classroom.

Searching Parameters: Starting with a free text search, then the user can narrow their results by theme, subject, language, age, rating, format and country.

Content: This portal seems to be a rather new one, as it currently features around 1000 resources.

Robotic related Content: No direct robotic content is available.

5. Platform Based Repository

Some robotic platform vendors offer repositories where people can share their activities with the platform. Beside Lego (Lego) and Arduino (Arduino) there are two interesting repositories to mention:

- **Dash and Dot** (Dot, 2015) offers a number of lesson plans for teachers, also with the possibility of allowing teachers to upload their own lesson plan. Each lesson plan is tagged with the subject domain and the grade it can be used with. Some of the lesson plans are free of charge, with others being accessible with a subscription.
- **Sphero** (Sphero, 2015) includes a “lightning lab” which is a growing community of makers, students, and instructors. Lightning Lab is your hub to create, contribute, and learn with Sphero robots. Further to this, one can download classic lesson plans in PDF format, which include student, teacher guide and worksheets.

CONCLUSIONS FROM REPOSITORIES ANALYSIS

The analysis of the above-listed educational robotics and science portals clearly shows there is still potential for another market player in the sense that none of them score a perfect 5 in everything. All of this was taken into account when we were building the first version of our ER4STEM repository.

7 USE CASES

In this section we explain different use cases that were created to help ensure that the stakeholders using the repository will enjoy a platform that was created with their needs in mind.

The below matrix shows the link between the use case and the stakeholders.

Use Case ID	Use Case	Stakeholder
1	Educator Teaching Young Students in Primary Level	Educator
2	Educator of different levels	Educator
3	Head of School wanting to bring about change	Head of School
4	Researcher focusing on robotics	Researcher
5	Robotics Organisation running events	Educational Robotic Organisation
6	Robotics conference organiser looking for new ideas	Robotic Conference Organiser
7	Parent of Primary School kids	Parent
8	Manager wanting to hire robotics experts	Managing Director

USE CASE 1:

I AM AN EDUCATOR TEACHING YOUNG STUDENTS IN PRIMARY LEVEL AND I AM LOOKING...

- To find information on how to make use of the new robot the IT department gave us to use in the classroom. Not sure where to start, or how to use this. I do not have a lot of programming knowledge.
- For educational program that I can apply in my everyday work;
- For organizations that can suggest and show me ways to teach my students technology or science;
- For materials/ devices (price and store) and where I can buy them at an affordable price for teaching my class technology/ science...;
- For curricula (incl. visual materials) for activities that teach my class Team Work, Communication, Creativity;
- For matrix or guidelines how to develop some elements of educational technology, i.e. using Minecraft, hangouts, Facebook.... how to set up educational goals, how to choose content, environment, etc.;

- For accessible (easy to find and easy to read/ prepare) materials to make my teaching more interesting for pupils.

USE CASE 2:

I AM AN EDUCATOR AND I WOULD LIKE TO:

- Compare available platforms, and to decide between the most suitable one based on my needs;
- Find tutorials to explain how to use a specific platform;
- Find new activities that I could use for a particular platform;
- Share my activity with others;
- Comment on others' activities about my experience;
- Find a way to bring technology into my classroom that can be used as a tool, the kids and the activity being in the center and the tool being a supporting actor;
- Find a way to link my curriculum topics to educational technology (robotics) activities;
- Excursions to companies in STEM fields;
- Find a way to teach mathematics concepts hands-on;
- Find a way to teach mathematics concepts with real cases (linked to life and not abstract);
- Find a way to introduce my curriculum concepts with real cases and hands-on approaches;
- Find an organization that can show me how to teach my class technology or science in a more involving way;
- Find sample of research goals – how to follow up on my students' interest towards technology, science, engineering;
- Find materials and good practices to help me out while identifying the personal learning style of my students;
- Find instruments to help me evaluate the attitude of my students towards the subject I teach;
- Find methodologies on how to include parents in the active support of educational robotics tools in general education;

USE CASE 3:

I AM A HEAD OF SCHOOL AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- Ways to get educational technology into my school (borrow it or exchange with other schools);
- Training for my teachers to use educational technology;

USE CASE 4:

I AM A RESEARCHER AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- Educational activities that I can use in my experiments;
- Activities set up that I can use in my own research;
- Contact with schools that are in my region to work with them;
- A place where I can share my research with others;
- A way to ask questions about some technical issues that I have found, and maybe others in the community have already faced;
- Other current European projects and recent publications about educational robotics that can be read for our research. I also want to find some good conferences about STEM, so we can attend in the future.

USE CASE 5:

I FORM PART OF AN EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS ORGANISATION AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- New prototypes that can be used in my teaching work (in the field of educational robotics) – guides and instructions;
- Tips on learning how to hack standard technological devices and broaden their applicability;
- Information on how to simplify or make more complex some available robotics projects so that they would fit appropriately the education needs of a respective age group;
- Guidelines and process description on how to involve educational institutions in the activities I already offer;
- Ways how I can share the projects I already offer to the world and how I can build a community around them;
- Educational robotics technology for my activities;
- Curricula and workshop concepts and contents;
- Customers (schools, parents);
- Networking activities for setting up new projects.

USE CASE 6:

I AM AN ORGANIZER OF A ROBOTICS CONFERENCE AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- A checklist of things I have to keep in mind when organizing a conference;
- Some ideas about activities that can be part of a conference;
- Schools, teachers and students who want to take part in a conference;
- Educational robotics technology that can be used for competitions;
- A venue for hosting the conference.

USE CASE 7:

I AM A PARENT OF PRIMARY SCHOOL KIDS AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- Educational technology that I can buy for my kids;
- Organisations that provide workshops with educational technology;
- Organisations that provide workshops that bring out creative problem-solvers;
- Organisations that provide workshops where kids talk about philosophical topics and combine it with problems they see in the world;
- Activities that teach my kids communication 1.0 (including teamwork, interdisciplinary thinking, ...);
- Finding out what my kids should learn, so that they can become independent happy adults.

USE CASE 8:

I AM A MANAGING DIRECTOR IN A MANUFACTURING COMPANY AND I AM LOOKING FOR:

- People that I could hire at an early age;
- Small projects that I could sponsor in schools and universities to have access to a good pool of people;
- Ways to contribute talents and skills that I think are necessary for people to work in my company.

CONCLUSIONS FROM USE CASES

The analysis of the above use case was useful as it showed which functionalities are being requested and why are people are wanting to have such an educational repository. The next chapter illustrates how different functions were mapped to each use case in order to come up with the requirements for development.

8 FUNCTIONALITY

In this chapter we explain which use cases match with each of the functionalities that were chosen to be implemented. The below matrix shows this link between the several use case and the functionalities. All the different functionalities mentioned in each use case were mapped onto the different requirements and synthesized in a way that the most common and requested ones were given priority in the development of the repository.

Use Cases	Functionality
ALL	Search Functionality
1, 2 ,4, 7	Filters / Tagging / Sorting
1, 2, 7	Rating/Feedback system
ALL	Login System
1, 2, 3, 4, 7	Good Practices (Activity Plans)
1, 2, 3, 5	Educational Framework
ALL	Database structure
4, 5	Academic papers
1,2,3	Curricula
5, 6	Competitions

In a brainstorming session that was held during the Malta partners meeting in September 2016, the partners focused on defining functionalities and how these would be used by stakeholders/ use case actors. The activities and results are summarised below.

1. All partners were asked to write what they would like the repository to do for them. The below are the main important points:
 - a. To help connect with other workshop instructors to exchange ideas and recruit kids
 - b. As a facilitator of Educational Robotics Workshops I want to use the repository in order to link workshops to the curriculum
 - c. Search via scientific factors
 - d. Evaluate the work done in workshops and deal with problematic behaviour
 - e. Search for activities linked to a particular technology
 - f. Activity plans to be used in class
 - g. To convince their principle to encourage more funds in schools
 - h. How to use robotics in class
 - i. Articles about educational repositories
 - j. Activities that can be used to test some aspects
 - k. Find contacts in the subject

2. Partners were later on grouped in threes. The role of each individual was to act either as an educator, a researcher or the portal. From this exercise a number of key functionality have been identified. These are summarised hereunder into different categories:
 - a. Search Functionality:
 - i. There should be a strong link between the activity plans' structure and how the data can be found on the repository. Should be strongly linked to the search feature.
 - ii. Search (by the user) should either be very specific or non-specific.
 - iii. Suggestions to be given to user to improve search results - e.g: "Do you want material for large groups?"
 - b. Filters / Tagging / Sorting:
 - i. Which technologies?
 - ii. Where do you get them from?
 - iii. How much do they cost?
 - iv. Rent or Share?
 - v. Level of experience needed by teacher
 - vi. Size of recommended teams (2/3 people per group)
 - vii. Duration of workshop
 - viii. Gender Filtering / STEM interest / Evaluation Method used - Linked to activity plan
 - ix. Standardised tags/ fields are required
 - x. Sort by objective - Girls get Interested / STEM, etc.
 - xi. Define on which basis to sort/filter and also pagination
 - c. Rating/Feedback system
 - i. Identification of the "best" resources/workshops/competitions - can be linked to rating system
 - ii. Researchers questions & answers - feedback given by community / papers
 - d. Login System
 - i. Login should be made using Google Profile / Facebook, etc.
 - ii. Registration for updates/news for the particular activity plan - via the application itself not via email
 - e. Good Practices
 - i. Engineering robots vs Blackbox robots - Good Practices
 - ii. How to handle students with learning difficulties in a mixed ability class - hints and examples on how to deal with them - Inclusion practise
 - f. Data
 - i. User Profiles - based on these profiles the interface can change (teacher/researcher)
 - ii. Glossary - linked to terms linked to activity plan/resources
 - iii. Videos - how other teachers implemented this
 - iv. Sharing of data - that includes sensitive data/items and copyrighted materials - Terms & Conditions are needed - Censorship needed?
 - v. Report button
 - vi. Checklists/Forms needed / Processes / Things needed
 - vii. Resources should have a hyperlink to more details - Short description about workshop should be present
 - viii. Data should be re-usable and customizable to be reused (editable)

ix. Collecting people out of school - Motivating to come to workshops

From all the ideas generated here is a list of the features and functionality that were decided that the repository will contain and which formed the basis of our development roadmap.

1. Direct link with the ER4STEM Framework
2. Link with the ER4STEM Activity Plan
3. Multi-language
 - English
 - Bulgarian
 - Greek
 - German
4. Responsive template
 - Works on desktop computer / tablets / mobile phones
5. Profile
 - Login using social media (Google, Facebook etc..)
 - Notifications
 - i. Update to “liked” resource - When someone like an activity plan that you liked you will get a notification...or when it is your activity plan
 - ii. New resources added
 - iii. Someone commented on their resources
 - iv. Delete account -> ask person if their activity plans should be deleted
 - Badges for contributors
 - i. Level 1 - Novice - When someone submits 1 activity plan
 - ii. Level 2 - Apprentice -
 - iii. Level 3 - Practitioner
 - iv. Level 4 - Expert
 - v. Level 5 - Moderator - Manual approval
6. Search functionality
 - Keywords e.g Maths
 - Open Sentences e.g Activities for Girls
7. Filter functionality
 - Age
 - Cost
 - Duration
 - Technology
 - Language
8. Advanced Search
 - Keyword
 - Subject
 - Age
 - Language
 - Domains
 - Programming Language
9. Resource Sorting
 - By Name
 - By Subject
 - By Popularity / Views
 - By Age
 - By Downloads
 - By Cost

10. Rating System -> with starts from 1 to 5
11. Commenting System
 - This is Give your Feedback - Post Activity
12. Sharing Functionality
 - By users to different means; Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Email etc.
13. Glossary
 - Linked directly from activity plans -> Based on the Glossary done.
14. Tagging
 - For linking of different activities together
 - i. Framework is linking activity plan together
15. Activity Plans
 - Submit own activity plans (based on point 2)
 - Edit / Download activity plan to be reused
 - Activity plan can be downloadable in PDF
 - Allows for uploading of supporting documents: PPTs, Videos etc.

Other important aspect of the repository include:

- Handling of sensitive data and copyright issues
- Crediting the original contributor - When copied "Original Contributor should be visible"
- User-friendly
 - Easy-to-navigate
 - Multi-browser support
 - Multi-language

8.1 WIREFRAMES

With any programming and software development it is advisable to focus first on the visual interface in order to be able to have a structured conversation with users and co-developers before actually starting to write code. This follows the ethos of Rapid Prototyping Development and saves multiple and costly iterations later on. For the creation of the ER4STEM repository a series of schematic graphical user interfaces, aka, wireframes that have been designed starting from the basis of the activity plan template. During a brainstorming session held in Malta, the activity plan was split into pieces, and grouping took place to ensure that an easy-to-use and user friendly approach is implemented when it comes for the users to upload an activity plan.

HOME RESOURCES ABOUT CONTACT

SEARCH RESOURCES

SEARCH [input] [magnifying glass] AGE [dropdown] TECHNOLOGY [dropdown] DOMAIN/SUBJECT [dropdown] LANGUAGE [dropdown] [ADVANCED SEARCH](#)

- LESSON PLANS
- COMPETITIONS
- WORKSHOPS
- OTHERS

SORT BY: Ranking / Age / Most Downloads

	NAME OF RESOURCE SUBJECT AGE: 10-15 AUTHOR	MORE INFO EN GR MT BG DE 68 50 30	
	NAME OF RESOURCE SUBJECT AGE: 10-15 AUTHOR	MORE INFO EN GR MT BG DE 68 50 30	
	NAME OF RESOURCE SUBJECT AGE: 10-15 AUTHOR	MORE INFO EN GR MT BG DE 68 50 30	

[HOME](#)
[RESOURCES](#)
[ABOUT](#)
[CONTACT](#)

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITY PLAN

TYPE OF ACTIVITY Lesson Plan

DOMAINS

SCIENCE	BUSINESS
TECHNOLOGY	ENGINEERING
MATHEMATICS	ARTS

CURRICULUM ALIGNED

EN GR MT BG DE PDF DOWNLOAD

68 50 30

AUTHOR _____

WHERE DOES THIS FIT IN THE ER4STEM FRAMEWORK?

WHO? WHERE? HOW LONG?

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

TECHNOLOGY

LEARNING AND TEACHING

DESCRIPTION OF ACTIVITIES

ASSESSMENT

ATTACHMENTS / SUPPORTING MATERIALS

VIEWING AN ACTIVITY PLAN

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN STEP 1 of 7

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITY PLAN

LANGUAGE [CHOOSE LANGUAGE](#)

TYPE OF ACTIVITY LESSON PLAN WORKSHOP COMPETITION RESEARCH / PAPER

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE: Name of Activity / Summary / Language and Type are **compulsary**

HOME RESOURCES ABOUT CONTACT

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN STEP 2 of 7

DOMAINS

SCIENCE	<input type="checkbox"/>	BUSINESS	<input type="checkbox"/>
TECHNOLOGY	<input type="checkbox"/>	ENGINEERING	<input type="checkbox"/>
MATHEMATICS	<input type="checkbox"/>	ARTS	<input type="checkbox"/>

CURRICULUM ALIGNED

DEFINE CONCEPT AND COUNTRY:

SUBJECT MATHS PHYSICS CHEMISTRY HISTORY *

SAVE AND CONTINUE SAVE AND EXIT

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE: Subject field is only displayed if Curriculum Aligned is checked * This will be in structured in 3 layers

HOME RESOURCES ABOUT CONTACT

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN - WHO? WHERE? HOW LONG?

STEP 4 of 7

GENDER GIRLS BOYS BOTH

AGE GROUP Min. Age - Max. Age

CLASS SIZE Small (1-10) Medium (11-20) Large (21+)

(IDEAL) GROUP SIZE No Groups 2 3 4

(IDEAL) GROUPING SUGGESTIONS Mixed Ability Mixed Gender Mixed Specialties

PRIOR KNOWLEDGE Yes No *if Yes, user will need to elaborate

DEFINE KNOWLEDGE

DESIGNED ALSO FOR STUDENTS WITH: ADD Dyslexia Dyscalculia Other

OTHER

ENVIRONMENT Lab Open Space Hall Classroom Indoor Outdoor

STYLE OF ROOM:

DURATION: Number of Sessions Duration of Each Session(Minutes) TOTAL: (X)

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE:

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN - TECHNOLOGY STEP 5 of 7

TECHNOLOGY USED: mBot Dash and Dot Thymio 2 Robotics Dream MOSS LEGO Mindstorms
 Other

PRICE PER KIT: €1- €50 €51 - €100 €101 - €150 €151 - €300 €301 - €500 €500+

PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE: Drag / Drop Scratch: Open SIM C++ Python Java C Arduino

TECHNOLOGY NEEDED: Computers Tablets / Mobile

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE: "Others" will be suggested to be added as part of the framework.

HOME RESOURCES ABOUT CONTACT

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN - DESCRIPTION OF ACTIVITIES

STEP 6 of 7

TITLE: _____

TYPE: Introductory Reflection Assessment Evaluation Exploration Experimentation
 Construction Other: _____

DURATION: minutes / hours

DESCRIPTION: _____

What does the robot perform? What do the students do? How does the robot look like? How does it behave? What is needed for this activity?

TEACHING METHOD: TAG +
 LEARNING OUTCOME: TAG +

This will have the learning outcomes (both from disciplinary and skills) created in step 3

SAVE AND CONTINUE SAVE AND EXIT

+ Add New Activity

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE: The teaching methods done here, will have a direct link to the framework ontology. More than 1 activity can be done here. An assessment activity must be present. Make sure that all learning outcomes have been linked with an activity.

HOME RESOURCES ABOUT CONTACT

NAME OF ACTIVITY PLAN - ATTACHMENTS / SUPPORTING MATERIAL STEP 7 of 7

WORKBOOK: CHOOSE FILE... UPLOAD FILE

MANUAL: CHOOSE FILE... UPLOAD FILE

PRESENTATIONS: CHOOSE FILE... UPLOAD FILE

SUPPORTING NOTES: CHOOSE FILE... UPLOAD FILE

OTHERS: CHOOSE FILE... UPLOAD FILE

SAVE AND CONTINUE SAVE AND EXIT

SUBMITTING AN ACTIVITY PLAN - Users need to be logged in

NOTE: Users will be able to upload different files and also tag them according to type, such as manual etc..

8.2 ACTIVITY PLAN ALIGNMENT

In the final stages of the project, the repository was fully aligned with the third year activity plan. This ensures that the creation of activity plans online is aligned according to the pedagogical approach proposed. Please refer to the work done in Work package 4 - Pedagogical Activities

8.3 INTERFACE DESIGN

Based on the project logo and branding guidelines, after the implementation of the wireframes, the interface started taking shape.

The below is a screenshot of homepage of the website.

The screenshot shows the ER4STEM website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Framework, Resources, Language, and Login. Below the navigation bar is a large banner image of children working with a robot, with the text 'ER4STEM The Robotics Repository'. A search bar is present with a search button and an 'Advanced search' link. Below the banner, there is a 'Sort By' dropdown menu set to 'Name'. On the left side, there is a 'Filter the results' section with several filter categories: 'Price per Kit' (ranging from No Cost to €500+), 'Duration (minutes)' (with Min and Max input fields), and 'Technology Used' (listing various robotics kits like Arduino, Dash & Dot, Hedgehog, Lego WeDo, LEGO Mindstorms, mBot, MOSS, Other, Robotic Dreams, SLurtles, and Thymio 2). An 'Apply Filters' button is located below these filters. The main content area displays a list of search results under the 'Workshops' category. Each result includes a title, subject, age range, author, and statistics for views and downloads. Each result also has links for 'More Info' and 'Download', and a share icon.

Workshops	Competitions	Research/Paper
Writing your name with a robot Subject Information Technology , Technology Age: 7-18 Author: Julian Angel		More Info Download Language: English Views: 213 Downloads: 0
Park the robot Subject Maths Age: 12-15 Author: Dimitris Diamantidis		More Info Download Language: English Views: 152 Downloads: 0
Robotics Workshop with LEGO Mindstorms Subject Other Age: 8-13 Author: Lisa Schuster		More Info Download Language: German Views: 50 Downloads: 0
Dash and Dot on a mission on Mars Subject Arts , Information Technology Age: 11-15 Author: Justyna Szczepańska		More Info Download Language: English Views: 57 Downloads: 0
Learning Robotics with Dash and Dot Subject Information Technology Age: 11-13 Author: Joanna Pullicino		More Info Download Language: English Views: 74 Downloads: 0

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9 DEVELOPMENT

This chapter explains the different approaches taken for the programming and technical development of the ER4STEM Repository

9.1 TECHNICAL FRAMEWORK

Due to the specific functionality that needed to be implemented in the ER4STEM repository the Laravel framework was used as a basis for the development of the repository.

Laravel is a web application framework with expressive, elegant syntax. Laravel attempts to take the pain out of development by easing common tasks used in the majority of web projects, such as authentication, routing, sessions, and caching.

Laravel is accessible, yet powerful, providing powerful tools needed for large, robust applications. A superb inversion of control container, expressive migration system, and tightly integrated unit testing support give you the tools you need to build any application with which you are tasked.

9.2 DATABASE STRUCTURE

The database was designed to support the implementation of the functionalities and requirements collected during the previous phases. The following diagrams illustrate the database structure of the repository and how tables are linked together. MySQL technology was used for the implementation.

9.3 CONTENT - ACTIVITY PLANS/WORKSHOPS

The content on the ER4STEM repository is user-generated content. This means that the content will come from the end user. After ensuring that the activity plan implementation was complete, all the partners uploaded their own activity plans that they have created during the project implementation period. This has helped in ensuring that when a user navigates through the repository, they can already find some activity plans available.

9.4 FEATURES

As mentioned in chapter 8, the repository consists of different features to fulfill the scope of the repository. All these features ensure that a user-friendly repository was made available for the stakeholder.

The below section describes how each feature of the platform works, with related illustrations / screenshots.

9.4.1 Home Page

The ER4STEM repository can be accessed from <https://repository.er4stem.com>.

The website also has an SSL certificate installed to ensure the user that the data transfer is done in a secure manner.

This domain was chosen as it can be easily used for dissemination purposes, and users would find it easy to remember this URL.

The homepage consist of the menu, the quick search functionality, and shows some of the activity plans available on the repository.

9.4.2 Sign Up / Login

When a user presses on the Login menu, they will easily find the options to either:

- Login
- Sign Up
- Request a new password
- Sign In with Facebook
- Sign Up Button

Upon pressing on the “Sign Up” link, the user will be taken to the register page

(<http://repository.er4stem.com/register>). From this page, the user needs to insert the Full Name, Email Address, Password and a confirmation of the password.

Once they insert all the correct information, the account will be created and the user can enjoy further features of the portal.

9.4.3 Link with ER4STEM Framework

The ER4STEM Framework has both a standalone section in the repository (see above) as well as being linked from each and every Activity Plan to the side of the Activity Plan example (image below in section 9.4.4).

The ER4STEM framework aims to make explicit the connection between pedagogical strategies, robotics and 21st century skills providing processes and tools to guide stakeholders on the critical use of robotics in education. Moreover, it situates the educational use of robotics in constructionist learning activities for children both inside and outside of school in which, they:

- Collaborate within and between teams
- Creatively engage with challenges in STEM domains
- Engage in critical thinking through reflection
- Have opportunities to learn how to recover from failure
- Gain a sense of achievement

These activities are taking place in shared spaces with mediating artefacts (aka robots), teachers and children are able to challenge existing classroom norms and attitudes towards learning (in STEM and in general), in order to develop and maintain young people's interest in STEM subjects and careers.

To achieve this, the ER4STEM framework provides four components that are the result of the work done in ER4STEM:

- Ontology of Educational Robotics
- Tools: ER4STEM web-repository, ER4STEM activity template and activity blocks, and ER4STEM generic curricula.
- ER4STEM pedagogical principles
- Processes for Workshop and Conference for young people.

9.4.4 ER4STEM Activity Plan - Viewing an activity plan

Robotics Workshop with LEGO Mindstorms

Author: Lisa Schuster

Weeks: 01
Downloads: 0

Author: Lisa Schuster

Where does this fit in the ER4STEM Framework?

Type of Activity: Workshop
Curriculum Aligned: not aligned

Subject: Other

Curriculum and Country: German

Language: German

Domains:

Science: 0	Business: 0
Technology: 10	Engineering: 6
Mathematics: 0	Arts: 0
Social Issues: 0	Life Skills: 0

OBJECTIVES AND SKILLS

Subject Related

No subject

Skills Learning Outcomes

No skills Outcomes

ARTIFACTS

WHO? WHERE? HOW LONG?

INTERACTIONS

TECHNOLOGY

LEARNING AND TEACHING

HOW TO

ASSESSMENTS

ATTACHMENTS / SUPPORTING MATERIALS

FEEDBACK

When a user selects an activity plan (workshop), they will be able to see detailed information about that particular workshop. This is in line with the activity plan template created for the ER4STEM project, however they are visualised in different sections to ensure that a user can access the information in a friendly manner.

These sections are:

- Basic Information
- Objectives and Skills
- Artifacts
- Who? Where? How Long?
- Interactions
- Technology
- Learning and Teaching
- How To

- Assessments
- Attachments/Supporting Materials
- Feedback

In this view, the user can also see where the activity plan fit in relationship to the ER4STEM Framework.

When a user is logged in, they can also see “Create a copy” of this plan. This allows the user to make a copy of the same activity plan and adapting it according to

their needs. When a user copies an activity plan, the original contributor, will still be credited.

9.4.5 ER4STEM Activity Plan - Submitting an activity plan

Step 1 of 9 - Basic information

Title: *

Summary: *
Max. 2000 characters.

Author:
 Testing Surname

Language: *
English

Type of Activity *
 Workshop Competition Research/Paper

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On the ER4STEM repository the users also have the possibility to submit and share with other educators/stakeholders their own activity plan. Users are able to submit an activity plan when they are logged in to the portal.

Domains

Choose categories and give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the following domains.

In order to guide users, a better a tool tip helps to understand what is meant by each and every section of the Activity Plan. Hovering with the mouse on the little (i) at the side gives a simple explanation of what it is.

From the Profile menu, the user can navigate to “Submit New Activity Plan” to start sharing their activity plan. This process is split into 9 different steps, to make it easier for the user and not to give up when they see a very long form.

At each step, the user can either press “Save and Continue” or “Save and Exit”. This will allow the user to stop at any point in time, and then continue submitting the activity plan at a later stage.

9.4.6 Multi-Language

The ER4STEM repository is available in 7 different languages: English, Bulgarian, Czech, German, Greek, Turkish and Italian. The last 2 languages were provided by external contributors who joined one of the webinars.

9.4.7 Responsive Template

The Repository was built in a responsive way to ensure that whether one is looking at it via a desktop computer, a mobile phone or a tablet, the layout will always adjust to accommodate the screen size - portrait or landscape. Here are 2 photos of the ER4STEM repository being used on a mobile phone.

9.4.8 User Profile

The User profile section allows the registered users of the repository to view their profile and manage the activity plans they have created. Moreover, it gives them the possibility to submit a new plan and look at the resources they would have marked as favourites.

As mentioned in 9.4.19 it is also possible to delete the user account and all their data completely in order to be fully compliant with GDPR issues.

9.4.9 Notifications

Notifications are given to the users when someone likes their activity plan or else rates it or gives a comment. This facility is a “push” notification that would get to the users similar to how notifications appear in social media websites.

9.4.10 Badges for Contributors

There are different levels of badges that one can get by being a contributor to the ER4STEM repository. For every action users can do on the repository, they are allocated points and the respective badges are applied. There are in total 5 Levels as follows:

- i. Level 1 - Novice - When someone submits 1 activity plan
- ii. Level 2 - Apprentice
- iii. Level 3 - Practitioner
- iv. Level 4 - Expert
- v. Level 5 - Moderator - {Requires additional Manual approval}

9.4.11 Search Functionality

The easiest way to find the best activity plans is to search the resources using the search function that is available at the top of every screen

9.4.12 Filter Functionality

Filter the results

Price per Kit

- No Cost
- €1 - €50
- €51 - €100
- €101 - €150
- €151 - €300
- €301 - €500
- €500 +

Duration (minutes)

Min Max

Technology Used

- Arduino
- Dash & Dot
- Hedgehog
- Lego WeDo
- LEGO Mindstorms
- mBot
- MOSS
- Other
- Robotic Dreams
- SLurtles
- Thymio 2

Apply Filters

Results of the search function can be additionally filtered using the options at the side of the results that allow the user to choose to view only those resources that match those filters.

Based on our requirements analysis there are 3 filters that were asked as the most important - the price per kit, the duration of the activity plan (in minutes) and the technology used (which robotic kit).

9.4.13 Advanced and Visual Search

Similar to how easy it is to search with the open text box, it is also quite quick to open up the advanced search button and include additional options to search upon. The options that can be chosen are:

- Keyword
- Subject
- Domain
- Programming Language
- Age range
- Language (human)

Since a lot of people are visual, it is also possible to get to the required activity plan and educational resources by clicking through an expanding tree diagram that sorts the activity plans into different subjects, domains and types. A screenshot can be seen below:

the average rating is then calculated based on the number of votes a resource has received.

9.4.16 Post-Feedback System

Give Your Feedback

Interested moments

How did you react?

Unexpected moments

How did you react?

Evidences of student learning

Evidence files [Add a file](#)

[Choose file](#) No file chosen

Possible changes

[Submit Your Feedback](#) [Close](#)

Sharing of educational resources is a 2-way street and this is why we have implemented a feedback system where any educator who has implemented one of the activity plans in their school is able to give feedback and make suggestions for the improvement of the learning resource.

9.4.17 Favourite, Share and Download Functionality

Each resource can be liked, shared with others or else downloaded as a PDF file in order to have a simpler way of accessing it even in class without any internet connection.

9.4.18 Glossary

The glossary of terms is a helpful feature to allow users of the repository to understand the terms used in the ER4STEM framework and activity plans. The list of terms is explained in simple words to allow everyone to be able to understand their meaning.

9.4.19 Delete Your Account

Due to GDPR implementation after 25th May 2018 we are also giving the opportunity for users to completely delete their data including any Activity plans they might have created and shared.

Delete Your Account ✕

Please, select the elements you want to PERMANENTLY DELETE:

- user profile
- related activity plans

Proceed Cancel

9.5 Generic Educational Robotics Curriculum

During the ER4STEM project meeting in Malta on April 2018, ESI CEE proposed to visualise the Generic Curriculum Map within the repository with links to each activity plan. The Generic Curriculum Map has been developed with the following features.

- Graphically represent the Generic Curriculum as a ‘metro map’ showing how an educator could navigate through the educational robotics activity plans taking each of these educational paths, educational robotics activity plans being graphically represented as metro stations.
- Provide a short text explanation of the Generic Curriculum Map, the educational paths, as well as the mission of the Generic Curriculum elaborated under the ER4STEM project, namely to assist teachers in adapting various learning path, consisting of a set of educational robotics workshops or single activities within the workshops activity plans, that are suitable for their context, students, specific objectives and prior knowledge.
- Link each “stop” of the Generic Curriculum Map to the respective Activity Plan in the ER4STEM Repository.

TOWARDS A GENERIC CURRICULUM FOR EDUCATIONAL ROBOTICS IN STEM: FROM SCIENTIFIC CONCEPTS TO TECHNOLOGIES AND POWERFUL IDEAS

9.6 Competitions

Building robotics competitions has been a great way during the project of engaging students, teachers and schools in the wider educational robotics arena. Therefore the repository also has a section that explains how one should go about as a process to build such conferences and competitions. The following diagram explains the process and this section gives simple directions on a step by step manner.

9.7 Academic Papers / Publications

TITLE	YEAR	AUTHORS	ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS	CONFERENCE	JOURNAL	BOOK CHAPTER
Architectural Overview and Hedgehog in Use	2018	Clemens Koza, Martin Wolf, Daniel Frank, Wilfried Lepuschitz, and Gottfried Koppenssteiner	Robotics is a versatile tool for teaching STEM topics, as it supports various disciplines, skill sets and target audiences. However, controllers used in Educational Robotics are often limited in their use cases. In this regard, Hedgehog tries to be flexible by design. This paper introduces Hedgehog's architecture, currently implemented and future use cases, and experiences from our first Hedgehog workshops.	Raspberry Pi, Controller, Visual programming, Blockly, Python	International Conference on Robotics and Education RIE 2017		
Constructing the shortest path on a cylindrical surface	2017	Chronis Kyriagos, Ioannis Zartzos	Digital media warrant a reappraisal of established conceptual fields and a search for new ones densely providing access to powerful mathematical ideas. This study reports secondary students' meaning making around the notion of intrinsically defined curvature in space by means of a tool integrating programming, dynamic manipulation of variable values and a simulation of 3D space. The study involved 15 ninth grade school students' attempt to design the shortest path between two points on a cylindrical surface are presented in this paper. Camera perusal and zoom allow for a change of viewpoints of the constructed figure. The findings yield meanings around concepts notoriously difficult even in undergraduate mathematics, such as differential stereometry, limits and curvature as systematic trihedron state change.	Curvature, helix, stereometry, meaning-making, programmable media	CERME10		
Determining the Effect of Programming Language in Educational Robotic Activities	2017	Julian M. Angel-Fernandez and Markus Vincze	Robotics has been suggested as a field of high potential in education and with high expectancy to impact teaching from kindergarten to university. This paper presents a study conducted with the purpose to have a better understanding of the impact of programming languages among participants of a workshop. An activity, which encompasses ten exercises, was designed and we used three different programming languages (i.e. visual, blocky and text) to program the Thymio robot. A total of six workshops were held using this activity two for each programming language. Qualitative and quantitative data were collected in each workshop. The results suggest that describe the		8th IEEE International Symposium on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN).		

The Research Papers developed by ER4STEM are also listed as additional resources in the repository under the heading Research/Papers from the top menu. The deliverables created by the project are also part of this section since many of these are public documents whose purpose was to help others understand more about educational robotics. A screenshot showing some of these publications is included above.

9.8 Community Area

One very important aspect of ER4STEM has always been making sure that the teachers and educators are empowered in order to be able to include robotics as a subject / medium for their classes. The consortium has done great work in order to make sure that top level resources are created and that they are placed online, however this is only one part of the story. The other is building a community around educational robotics that will make sure that this great work continues and that will provide a support network to each other. With this in mind, we have created an online Facebook Group for educational robotics enthusiasts and we are linking to it also from the repository, so that once teachers find the great materials and activity plans, they can also find other like minded colleagues that will be able to support them and assist them on a day to day basis. At the time of writing we had 250 followers within this community.

<https://www.facebook.com/er4stem/>

9.9 TESTING AND REFINEMENT

A testing sheet has been made available for both internal and external use. All the partners had the ability to test the platform on different devices and also at different stages of the project. This sheet was an easy method to ensure we collect the correct information and execute accordingly. The below image illustrates a snippet from the testing document. As defined hereunder, users had to insert the

date, devices, their name, issue/feature request and the status which is changed by the development team.

Date	Device	Tester	Issue/ Feature	Status
25/04/2017		Christina	In the activity plans we give a rating of the level of emphasis on concepts from each of the domains from 0-10, not 1-5	Complete
25/04/2017	Chrome - Windows	Carina	ER4STEM logo - expectation is that it is 'home' for site but takes to project website.	Complete
25/04/2017	Chrome - Windows	Carina	ER4STEM Framework page takes user to Ontology - what do they have to do with each other?	Complete
25/04/2017	Chrome - Windows	Christina	I don't like the ER4STEM logo leading to the ER4STEM project page and not the home page of the repository	Complete
25/04/2017	Firefox - Windows	Wilfried	Advanced search: the dropdown lists of subjects and languages should be in alphabetic order	Complete
25/04/2017	Firefox - Windows	Wilfried	User profile: where can I see my profile data and change it?	Complete
25/04/2017	Firefox - Windows	Wilfried	When not logged in, I have the main options: Home, ER4STEM Framework, Resources; When logged in, I have: Home, ER4STEM Framework, Profile; This change does not appear logic for me	Complete
25/04/2017	Google Chrome - Mac	Annalise	Remove - Resource repository	Complete
25/04/2017	Google Chrome - Mac	Annalise	Between Top menu and search - do a space for an image - homepage only - and this should have an "open" search function	Complete
25/04/2017	Google Chrome - Mac	Annalise	Remove "Search Resources" and place the search functionality in a "rounded box"	Complete
25/04/2017	Google Chrome - Mac	Annalise	http://repository.er4stem.com/new-activity - Do each section in a box - different background image	Complete

9.10 MAINTENANCE AND OPTIMIZATION

AcrossLimits will ensure the sustainability of the repository together with the other partners. Further information about this will be part of the final project management report at the end of Year 3 of the project.

9.11 TIMELINE / GANTT CHART

In Annex 3, one can find the deliverable gantt chart that was using during the project period that helped ensure that this deliverable and the implementation of the repository was kept on time.

10 CONCLUSION

The ER4STEM repository has been built throughout the project as the external representation and testament of the great research done during the lifetime of the project, and as a way to share this knowledge with the larger European community of educators.

It has achieved its aim of being a centralised repository aimed at teachers, robotics practitioners and researchers across Europe to help make resources for robotics education easily available and in helping educators make use of robotics during their lessons without being daunted by this prospect.

The ER4STEM repository will continue to be showcased and disseminated to the community even after the project has finished, thanks to the sustainability actions and plans of several of the partners.

11 APPENDICES

11.1 APPENDIX 1: SCIENTIX TEACHER WORKSHOP AGENDA

Name of Workshop: 10th Scientix Projects Workshop in the Future Classroom Lab

Date: 28th February 2016

Place: Brussels

Details: A 45-minute workshop on *“Teachers requirements to incorporate educational robotics activities in a classroom”*

Approximately 15 STEM teachers from Europe are expected to participate in the following workshop.

Adapted world café method

5 min - Introduction

- Explain workshop goal
- Split into groups of 2-3 people

10 min - Questions 1 (Group work)

Please introduce yourselves and answer following question together, note down findings

- Where are you from? How long have you been teaching? What subject(s) do you teach?
- What connections could there be between your subject(s) and robotics?

10 min - Questions 2 (Group work)

Please move to the next question and answer it together, note down findings

- If you could create or choose a tool to help you with your teaching, any tool that you imagine, how would it look like? What would be the most important features for you?

5 min - Individual work

Time for reflection and taking notes.

For our documentation, we would appreciate you filling out the summary sheet with your findings and ideas. The completion is voluntary. You can answer any question you like.

Experience in teaching: ____ years

Subjects taught:

Age group: -6 7-10 11-14 15-18 19+

If you could create or choose a tool to help you with your teaching, any tool that you imagine, how would it look like? What would be the most important features for you?

Further comments:

10 min - Discussion of all participants

Comparing findings, synergies, new ideas, updating your notes

5 min - Wrap up

45 minutes in total.

11.2 APPENDIX 2: ER4STEM - NEEDS ANALYSIS QUESTIONNAIRE

Explanation of “Repository”: This is an online portal/tool where a number of things/resources/items/files are stored and made accessible in one form or another.

What is your profession?

- Teacher / Educator
- School Management
- ICT Technician in School
- Robotics Enthusiast
- Other

If you are an educator: What age group do you teach?

- *Under 7*
- *7-10*
- *11-15*
- *16-18*
- *19+*

Do you already make use of Robots in your School?

If yes, what subjects do you use it for and which robotics are you using?

Which online resources/portals do you already make use in your teaching?

- *SCIENTIX*
- *OPENEDUCATIONEUROPA*
- *European Schoolnet*
- *EPALE*
- *OER Commons*
- *Others...please specify*

If you could create a tool/portal to help you improve your teaching methods, what would it do?
What would be the most important features for you?

Which of these features would you make use of in an Educational Repository (Portal) that would be dedicated to Robotics?

- Mobile Version (This is a mobile app which you can download on your Android / iPad or mobile phones)
- Web Application
- Link to the ER4STEM Generic Curriculum
- Multi Language
- Forum/Comment section
- Search Filters
- Videos
- Tutorials

- Examples / Success Stories
- Rating and comments
- Link to other repositories
- Teacher Submissions
- Teacher “favourites”
- Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources
- Integration and sharing with social media
- Badges
- Push Notifications

Which of the following resources would you like to see?

- Lesson plans / Activity Plans
- Workshops
- Curricula
- Conferences
- Pedagogical activities and innovation
- Educational Technologies
- Games using Robotics
- Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy
- Other artefacts
- Good Practices
- Evaluation methods
- Academic Papers and Research studies
- _____[Mention Others]_____

If you had to choose the filters by which you search resources? Which ones would you prefer? Sort from 1-6 (1 being the most important)

- Language
- Domain
- Duration
- Technology
- Age
- Difficulty
- Curriculum Subject
- _____[Mention Others]_____

11.3 APPENDIX 2: ER4STEM - NEEDS AND REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS (2016-06-01)

- RAW DATA

IP	Submission Date	What is your profession?	If you are an educator, what age group do you teach?	Do you already make use of robots in your school?	If yes, what subjects do you use it for and which robot technologies are you using?	Which online resources/portals do you already make use in your teaching?	If you could create a tool/portal to help you diversify your teaching approach, what would be the most important features you would include?	Which of these features would you make use of in a portal that would be dedicated to robotics?	Which of the following resources would you like to see?	If you had to choose the filters by which you search resources. Which ones would you prefer? Sort from 1-7 (1 being the most important)
84.114.246.16	2016-04-14 4:53	Teacher / Educator	15-18	Yes	We have just started Robotics courses: electronics and programming course. We are using Arduino and ArduBlock	Mehackit.org	Selfstudy material for students about basics, project ideas with some basic instructions, links to interesting projects to go on after course, chat possibility, a site where students can post for example videos about their robots	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Technology 2: Age 3: Difficulty 4: Duration 5: Curriculum Subject 6: Language 7: Domain
84.114.246.16	2016-04-14 4:34	Teacher / Educator	15-18	Yes	Just started course on Arduino	Learn.mehackit.org	Clear description for content	Mobile Version Web Application Multilanguage Search Filters Videos Tutorials Recommendation System	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Pedagogical activities and innovation Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Language 2: Duration 3: Technology 4: Age 5: Difficulty 6: Domain 7: Curriculum Subject
178.83.128.83	2016-04-14 4:12	Educational Researcher	11-14	Yes	Lego Mindstorm	None at all	models easy to implement as skills vary widely	Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher Submissions	Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class	1: Age 2: Domain 3: Technology 4: Language 5: Duration 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject
181.245.157.65	2016-04-13 16:2	Teacher / Educator	11-14	Yes	Math	None at all	Workshops	Multilanguage Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Language 3: Age 4: Difficulty 5: Technology 6: Domain 7: Duration

188.118.246.162	2016-04-01 16:22	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	Yes	Aduino, Lego mindstorm	None at all	something with sounds and moving pictures	Mobile Version Videos	Workshops Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices	1: Language 2: Technology 3: Age 4: Difficulty 5: Domain 6: Duration 7: Curriculum Subject
76.200.202.122	2016-03-31 11:11	Teacher / Educator	7-10 11-14	Yes	Summer school only at this point, but hope to expand into science.	The Lego Mindstorms EV3 Discovery Book: A Beginner's Guide to Building and Programming Robots	How to videos	Videos Tutorials Student success stories and examples of their projects	Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics	1: Language 2: Domain 3: Duration 4: Technology 5: Age 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject
76.200.202.122	2016-03-31 11:11		7-10 11-14	Yes	Summer school only at this point, but hope to expand into science.	The Lego Mindstorms EV3 Discovery Book: A Beginner's Guide to Building and Programming Robots	How to videos	Videos Tutorials Student success stories and examples of their projects	Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics	1: Language 2: Domain 3: Duration 4: Technology 5: Age 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject
141.8.98.76	2016-03-31 1:31	Teacher / Educator	11-14	No		None at all	I first need some more awareness. I need someone to guide me or inform me about the opportunities available first and not (as it happens at times) the same people attend/are involved. In terms of the portal, no excessive words and fun colours to stimulate the students.	Videos Tutorials	Workshops Conferences Good Practices	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Language 3: Domain 4: Duration 5: Technology 6: Age 7: Difficulty
89.210.10.145	2016-03-29 17:55	Teacher / Educator	7-10	Yes	- programming with scratch - making robots with lego we are using LEGO WeDo	None at all	- examples - QnA, FAQs for teachers - activity plans - competitions - workshops and online seminars - conferences	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Difficulty 4: Duration 5: Technology 6: Domain 7: Language

46.11.62.212	2016-03-29 8:54	Teacher / Educator	11-14	No		None at all	Worksheet with test papers and different experiments.	Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Age 3: Domain 4: Language 5: Difficulty 6: Technology 7: Duration
88.203.98.55	2016-03-29 7:48	Teacher / Educator	11-14	No		SCIENTIX	one which would facilitate assessment in class	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Conferences Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Language 2: Age 3: Curriculum Subject 4: Difficulty 5: Duration 6: Domain 7: Technology
92.251.16.19	2016-03-29 7:43	Teacher / Educator	Under 7 7-10	No		SCIENTIX	Interactive games	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Integration and sharing with social media Push Notifications	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Pedagogical activities and innovation Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Age 3: Language 4: Difficulty 5: Technology 6: Duration 7: Domain
78.133.45.190	2016-03-29 6:25	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	Yes	Robotics - Computer Studies / ICT... Lego MindStorms	SCIENTIX	user friendly, easy to share resources, free resources, inquiry based approach	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Integration and sharing with social media Push Notifications	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Difficulty 3: Language 4: Age 5: Duration 6: Technology 7: Domain

141.8.71.40	2016-03-29 5:57	Teacher / Educator	Under 7 7-10	No		SCIENTIX European Schoolnet	Easy access such as apps for students, parents and teachers	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Educational Technologies Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Difficulty 3: Technology 4: Duration 5: Language 6: Domain 7: Curriculum Subject
193.1.66.50	2016-03-29 5:07	Educational Researcher				None at all	Clear description of resources and how activities will work before downloading everything.	Web Application Forum/Comme nt section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendati on System Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Language 4: Technology 5: Domain 6: Duration 7: Difficulty
178.128.162.84	2016-03-25 2:39	Teacher / Educator	15-18	Yes	Programming, Environmental projects, LEGO EV3, Arduino Raspberry	SCIENTIX	Cross subject lesson plans	Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comme nt section Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class	1: Technology 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Difficulty 4: Age 5: Domain 6: Duration 7: Language
193.92.228.203	2016-03-23 13:4	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	Yes	I use Lego Mindstorms NXT and EV3 Education sets. Our students practice and improve their programming skills through robotics during computer science course. Also, in our school students have the opportunity to join robotic clubs and participate in WRO contests.	None at all	Variety of projects Discussion forum collaboration friendly user interface	Web Application Forum/Comme nt section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Language 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Technology 4: Difficulty 5: Duration 6: Age 7: Domain

217.30.100.196	2016-03-18 7:30	Teacher / Educator	19+	No		None at all	pictures with sounds; animations; speech engine.	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Difficulty 2: Language 3: Technology 4: Curriculum Subject 5: Domain 6: Duration 7: Age
2.232.253.187	2016-03-17 17:2	Teacher / Educator	11-14	No		European Schoolnet Edmodo	colours; interactivity; involvement of the students; control by the teachers	Mobile Version Web Application Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Badges	Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Technology 2: Language 3: Domain 4: Curriculum Subject 5: Age 6: Duration 7: Difficulty
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:25	Teacher / Educator	7-10	Yes	Lego WeDo, Probot, Beebot. During ICT lessons	None at all	Ideas for applying robotics to real life + cross curricular links. Ideas for various activities which can be done with limited resources	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Technology 3: Curriculum Subject 4: Difficulty 5: Language 6: Domain 7: Duration
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:23	School Management	7-10	Yes	Beebot for Maths	None at all	Case conferencing with schools abroad participating in an Erasmus project together.	Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies	1: Language 2: Age 3: Curriculum Subject 4: Domain 5: Duration 6: Technology 7: Difficulty
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:21	Teacher / Educator	Under 7 7-10	Yes	Bee bot constructa bot English and maltese lessons	None at all iLearn and eTwinning	Teacher + Child friendly (not like frontier)	Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Teacher "favourites" Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Duration 4: Domain 5: Difficulty 6: Technology 7: Language

141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:18	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	Yes	Yes, in after school activities. EVS Lego Mindstorm	None at all	See next question item	Mobile Version Web Application Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Link to other repositories	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Pedagogical activities and innovation Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class	1: Duration 2: Age 3: Difficulty 4: Technology 5: Domain 6: Language 7: Curriculum Subject
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:18	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	No		SCIENTIX European Schoolnet	Easy to filter information Clear instructions to reproduce it.	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Search Filters Tutorials Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Integration and sharing with social media	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Syllabus Competitions Games using Robotics	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Difficulty 3: Duration 4: Language 5: Technology 6: Age 7: Domain
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:14	School Management		No		SCIENTIX	tools to help in maths. Music making and artistic features	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Age 2: Difficulty 3: Language 4: Domain 5: Curriculum Subject 6: Duration 7: Technology
141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:12	School Management	15-18 19+	Yes	No, but we are working on a Level 2 programme on Robotics. The college already invested in a couple of Lego Mindstorms	None at all	Something which engages students into learning. Being 16+ students technology can be a motivator. Needs to be practical and interactive.	Mobile Version Web Application Multilanguage Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Language 2: Domain 3: Duration 4: Technology 5: Age 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject

141.8.35.54	2016-03-17 6:12		15-18 19+	Yes	No, but we are working on a Level 2 programme on Robotics. The college already invested in a couple of Lego Mindstorms	None at all	Something which engages students into learning. Being 16+ students technology can be a motivator. Needs to be practical and interactive.	Mobile Version Web Application Multilanguage Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Language 2: Domain 3: Duration 4: Technology 5: Age 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:43	Teacher / Educator	7-10	Yes	ict, science and maths. We have a beebot and a probot.	None at all	I would like to create online resources to upload in my virtual classroom	Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Link to other repositories Teacher "favourites"	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Difficulty 4: Language 5: Technology 6: Domain 7: Duration
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:43	Teacher / Educator	11-14	No		None at all	To perform scientific experiments visually.	Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Age 3: Language 4: Duration 5: Difficulty 6: Technology 7: Domain
78.133.124.146	2016-03-17 4:42	Teacher / Educator	15-18	No		None at all	Visual features such as interactive animations, and guided practicals for hands on approach. feedback methodologies to evaluate the students' engagement with the tool.	Mobile Version Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Difficulty 3: Language 4: Age 5: Domain 6: Technology 7: Duration

217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:42	Teacher / Educator	Under 7 7-10 11-14	No		European Schoolnet	A way to keep track of student progress and assign work accordingly	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Badges Push Notifications	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Language 2: Age 3: Difficulty 4: Technology 5: Curriculum Subject 6: Duration 7: Domain
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:41	School Management		No		None at all	Interactivity, fun, games, challenging activities.	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Technology 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Age 4: Domain 5: Difficulty 6: Language 7: Duration
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:41	Clerk		Yes	Science, IT	None at all	Frontier can be used for sharing and implementation of resources.	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Recommendation System	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Competitions Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Difficulty 3: Language 4: Technology 5: Duration 6: Domain 7: Curriculum Subject

185.5.51.84	2016-03-17 4:41	Teacher / Educator	15-18	Yes	Lego mind storms just bought-we are on the learning curve	Still learning mode	PV simulation and online simulation of the programmed robot	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Other artefacts Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Difficulty 2: Technology 3: Duration 4: Curriculum Subject 5: Language 6: Age 7: Domain
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:40	School Management		No		Moodle	More practical activities, involve parents and students.	Mobile Version Web Application Videos Tutorials Push Notifications	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Educational Technologies	1: Technology 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Age 4: Difficulty 5: Language 6: Domain 7: Duration
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:40	Elearning support teacher (Primary)	7-10	Yes	Mainly for Mathematics; BeeBots and a ProBot.	European Schoolnet	Child friendly; simple and straightforward	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class	1: Language 2: Age 3: Difficulty 4: Domain 5: Duration 6: Technology Subject 7: Curriculum Subject
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:39	Teacher / Educator	Under 7 7-10	No		SCIENTIX European Schoolnet	Resources & funds	Mobile Version Web Application Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Language 4: Technology 5: Domain 6: Difficulty 7: Duration
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:38	Teacher / Educator	11-14	Yes	Computing	None at all	Accessibility Different abilities Free of charge	Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites" Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices	1: Language 2: Duration 3: Technology 4: Age 5: Difficulty 6: Domain 7: Curriculum Subject

185.5.51.40	2016-03-17 4:37	Teacher / Educator	11-14	Yes	Computing	None at all	Levelled tasks from low level questions to high level questions	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher "Favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Age 2: Difficulty 3: Curriculum Subject 4: Duration 5: Technology 6: Language 7: Domain
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:37	School Management		No		None at all	User friendly Resources sharing facility Online courses	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Forum/Comment section Search Filters Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Link to other repositories Teacher Submissions Teacher "Favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources Recommendation System Integration and sharing with social media Badges	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Conferences Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Technical reviews on which robots are best to buy Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Language 4: Difficulty 5: Duration 6: Technology 7: Domain
217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:37	ICT Technician in School		Yes	Computer studies & digital literacy. Technology used is VE 3 lego mindstorms	None at all	Sharing if resources from common and specialized subjects.	Mobile Version Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Teacher Submissions Push Notifications	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Process to design an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Curriculum Subject 2: Age 3: Difficulty 4: Duration 5: Technology 6: Language 7: Domain

217.30.100.196	2016-03-17 4:36	Teacher / Educator	11-14 15-18	Yes	Computing, NKT mindstorms	SCIENTIX	User friendly and good for all streams	Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher Submissions	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Competitions Pedagogical activities and innovation Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to evaluate an activity in class Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Domain 2: Language 3: Duration 4: Technology 5: Age 6: Difficulty 7: Curriculum Subject
185.5.51.50	2016-03-17 4:36	School Management		Yes	Scratch Lego Mindstorms EV3 (whole range incl extension kits, pneumatics kits etc) Lego Wedo Beebots Probots Lego software	OPENEDUCATIO NEUROPEA	Blended Learning Enquiry based learning Flipped classroom	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Rating and comments Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites"	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Conferences Competitions Educational Technologies Games using Robotics Good Practices Academic Papers and Research studies	1: Age 2: Technology 3: Curriculum Subject 4: Difficulty 5: Language 6: Duration 7: Domain
185.5.51.21	2016-03-17 4:36	School Management		No		None at all	To help teaching maths outside the box.	Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Videos Tutorials Best Practice Examples / Success Stories Teacher "favourites" Mailing notifications about new or interesting resources	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class Process to develop a curriculum Process to evaluate an activity in class	1: Age 2: Curriculum Subject 3: Difficulty 4: Language 5: Duration 6: Technology 7: Domain
46.11.224.66	2016-03-17 4:36	Teacher / Educator		Yes	lego mindstorm with form 3 computing students	None at all	Accessibility and free of charge	Mobile Version Web Application Link to Subject Topic/ Syllabus Multilanguage Videos Tutorials Teacher Submissions Teacher "favourites"	Lesson plans / Activity Plans Workshops Syllabus Competitions Games using Robotics Good Practices Process to design an activity in class	1: Language 2: Age 3: Domain 4: Technology 5: Difficulty 6: Duration 7: Curriculum Subject

